

1 **Slowly digestible starch in fully gelatinized material is structurally driven by**
2 **molecular size and A and B1 chain lengths**

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26 **Abstract**

27 The objective of this study was to obtain structure-digestion relationships of fully
28 gelatinized starch. Twelve starch samples with marked fine structural differences (HPLC-
29 SEC) were studied for their retrogradation behavior (thermal and rheological properties
30 of starch gels) and *in vitro* digestibility. A reduction in the digestion rate during storage
31 for 7 days was observed in all samples and, interestingly, this reduction was particularly
32 evident in sago (64.7 %), potato (57.3 %), pea (55.1 %) and acid-converted maize (ACM,
33 51.6-51.8 %) starches. Results indicated two potential interactions that may result in
34 slowly digestible supramolecular structures: 1) double helices between external A and B1
35 chains of DP at peak maximum ≥ 15.5 Glucose Units (perhaps involving internal long
36 chains) that also are prone to forming intermolecular associations [high relative drop in
37 the storage modulus (G') during heating of 7 days-stored gels] and; 2) interactions of
38 small molecular size acid-hydrolyzed starch molecules that may be more mobile and
39 easily aligned.

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43 Keywords: starch; retrogradation; chain length distribution; sago; acid-converted maize;

44 digestion;

45

46 **1 Introduction**

47 Starch, being the principal component in cereals, tubers and pulses, is the major
48 polysaccharide related to postprandial glycaemia and glycemic index of foods. Glucose
49 response is frequently described by its glycemic index (GI) or glycemic response, i.e.,
50 rapid increase of the postprandial blood glucose, and many studies have linked low GI
51 diets with reduced risk of developing type 2 diabetes and cardiovascular disease (Jenkins
52 et al., 2002). In humans, starch is successively hydrolyzed by salivary and pancreatic α -
53 amylase in the mouth and small intestine, and then to glucose by the mucosal α -
54 glucosidases, and differences in the glycemic response depend highly on the rate and
55 extent to which starch is digested.

56 Native starch naturally exists in the form of starch granules with different properties,
57 including surface porosity and semi-crystalline structure. Based on their X-ray diffraction
58 pattern, starches can be classified into three types: A-, B- and C- (combination of A and
59 B-allomorphs) type. A-type starches encompass those from cereals, and many possess
60 surface pores and channels, whereas such pores do not exist in B-type starches, which
61 include those from tubers. This macrostructural difference is important during digestion
62 as digestive enzymes enter the channels and digest starches gradually in an inside-out
63 manner. In this way, A-type starches are slowly digestible (Zhang, Ao, & Hamaker, 2006;
64 Zhang, Venkatachalam, & Hamaker, 2006) and B-type starches are inherently resistant.
65 This native starch macromolecular structure, acting as a natural physical barrier to
66 enzyme digestion, is lost in many foods because of hydrothermal processes, such as
67 cooking, boiling and baking, among others, which lead to partial or complete starch
68 gelatinization (Varriano-Marston, Ke, Huang, & Ponte, 1980; Martinez, Roman, &
69 Gomez, 2018). An exception to this is high amylose starch (HAMS), which have been
70 reported to retain its native structure (assessed by X-ray diffraction pattern) during baking

71 (Hoebler, Karinthi, Chiron, Champ, & Barry, 1999). The amorphous structure of
72 gelatinized starch results in far greater availability of α -amylase binding sites, which
73 makes the substrate more susceptible to enzyme hydrolysis (Baldwin et al., 2015) and
74 results in a wide array of food products with high GI (Foster-Powell, Holt, & Brand-
75 Miller, 2002).

76 A great deal of effort has been put forth to decrease starch bioaccessibility using a variety
77 of methods, although many entail the use of expensive enzymes (Shin et al., 2004; Shi,
78 Cui, Birkett, & Thatcher, 2003; Han et al., 2006; Ao et al., 2007; Guraya, James, &
79 Champagne, 2001), or physical modifications such as heat-moisture treatment (Lee &
80 Moon, 2015), where the positive effects on digestion are often lost during further thermal
81 processing unless using HAMS (Hoebler et al., 1999).

82 Starch retrogradation, defined as the re-association of amylose and amylopectin chains
83 into ordered structures that are different from the original, is known to result in a reduction
84 of the rate and extension of starch digestion, depending on the main constituent involved.
85 Amylose double helices (retrograded amylose) are known to be enzymatically resistant
86 and yield resistant starch (RS) (Haralampu, 2000; Patel et al., 2017), whereas retrograded
87 amylopectin has been attributed to the formation of slowly digestible starch (SDS) [Cui
88 & Oates, 1997; Farhat et al., 2001; Zhang, Sofyan, & Hamaker, 2008; Borah, Deka, &
89 Duary, (2017). In a study on rice starch digestibility and amylopectin fine structure
90 parameters, Benmoussa, Moldenhauer and Hamaker (2007) showed that the lowest
91 content of rapidly digestible starch (RDS) was found in rice cultivars with high
92 proportions of amylopectin with long chains. Zhang et al. (2008) found that higher content
93 of amylopectin with longer chains promoted formation of SDS through retrogradation in
94 starches from maize mutants. Several authors have reported, albeit with no digestion
95 analysis, that longer amylopectin branches are more prone to form intra- and

96 intermolecular associations during cooling (Kohyama, Matsuki, Yasui, & Sasaki, 2004;
97 Matalanis, Campanella, & Hamaker, 2009; Jane & Chen, 1992). However, the combined
98 roles and synergies of multiple starch molecular features, including amylopectin fine
99 structure and amylose length, for controlling amylopectin and amylose retrogradation and
100 the rate of digestion are not evident. For example, Jane and Chen (1992), working with
101 reconstituted slurries of different amylopectins and amyloses, found that mixtures of
102 amylopectin with amylose of intermediate length (667 DP) resulted in the greatest gel
103 strength; yet, the structure-digestibility relationship was not investigated.

104 Despite extensive research conducted on starch structure-digestion relationships, a
105 mechanistic understanding of how SDS structurally forms in a fully gelatinized material
106 is still unclear. We hypothesized that certain starches found in nature inherently, or after
107 acid-conversion commonly used in some food applications, lead to the formation of SDS
108 after gelatinization. In this study, 12 starches with different structural features served as
109 a basis to elucidate structure-re-association relationships and their effect on starch
110 digestibility. The slow digestion property of these starches was investigated after full
111 gelatinization as determined by DSC, except for high amylose maize (HAM) starches,
112 whose slow digestion property could also be derived from ungelatinized material. HAM
113 starches have been reported to have conclusion temperatures of starch gelatinization (T_c)
114 up to 130 °C (Jane et al., 1999), which is not attainable with the conventional RVA used
115 in this study. Then, select starches were tested in a cake system to demonstrate this effect
116 in a real product.

117 **2. Materials and methods**

118 **2.1 Materials**

119 Maize, acid-converted maize, waxy maize, potato, waxy potato, rice, waxy rice, high
120 amylose maize and sago starches were generously supplied by Ingredion Inc.

121 (Bridgewater, NJ, USA), pea starch by Roquette (Lestrem, France) and wheat starch by
122 ADM (Chicago, IL, USA). α -Amylase [(1 \rightarrow 4)- α -glucan-4-glucanohydrolase] from
123 porcine pancreas (type VI-B pancreatic α -amylase, Sigma A3176) was purchased from
124 Sigma-Aldrich (St Louis, MO, USA). Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) and lithium bromide
125 (ReagentPlus) were purchased from VWR (Radnor, PA, USA) and Beantown Chemical
126 (Hudson, NH, USA), respectively. *Pseudomonas* sp. isoamylase (glycogen 6-
127 glucanohydrolase; EC 3.2.1.68) was purchased from Megazyme International Ltd. (Co.
128 Wicklow, Ireland).

129 **2.2 Methods**

130 **2.2.1. Molecular size and unit chain length distribution of amylose and amylopectin**

131 The molecular size distributions of fully branched and debranched starches were analyzed
132 in duplicate using a size exclusion chromatography (SEC) system (Agilent 1260 series,
133 Agilent Technologies, Waldbronn, Germany) equipped with a refractive index detector
134 (RID, 1260 RID, Agilent, Agilent Technologies, Waldbronn, Germany) following the
135 method of Cave, Seabrook, Gidley, and Gilbert (2009) with minor modifications. Starch
136 extraction was performed as in Syahariza, Li and Hasjim. (2010) with minor
137 modifications, involving the incubation of samples with protease (0.9 U/mL) in tricine
138 buffer (20 mg/mL, pH 7.5, 250 mM) at 37 °C for 30min.

139 For the fully branched size distribution (whole molecule), starch (8 mg) was dissolved in
140 1 mL DMSO solution containing 0.5% (w/w) lithium bromide (DMSO/LiBr) at 80 °C in
141 a thermomixer (Eppendorf, Hamburg, Germany) for 24 h. Samples were then precipitated
142 two times with absolute ethanol (10 mL) and re-dissolved in 0.05% DMSO/LiBr as in the
143 previous step. Samples were mixed and centrifuged at 4000 g for 10 min. Supernatant
144 was transferred into a SEC vial and then injected into GRAM 30 and 3000 columns (PSS
145 GmbH, Mainz, Germany) connected in series. These columns provided separation in the

146 range of 5×10^3 to $\sim 5 \times 10^6$ Da, corresponding to hydrodynamic radius (R_h) from ~ 0.5
147 to ~ 50 nm. The injection volume, flow rate, and temperature were $100 \mu\text{L}$, 0.3 mL/min ,
148 and $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, respectively. For the molecular size distribution of individual branches of
149 starch molecules, starch was dissolved in 1.5 mL DMSO/LiBr and treated in the same
150 way as fully branched samples. The recovered starch pellet was dissolved in 0.9 mL of
151 warm deionized water in a boiling water bath for 15 min , cooled down to room
152 temperature, and mixed with $5 \mu\text{L}$ sodium azide solution (40 mg/mL), 0.1 mL acetate
153 buffer (0.1 M , $\text{pH } 3.5$), and $2.5 \mu\text{L}$ isoamylase in sequence. The debranching reaction was
154 carried out at $37 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 3 h . The debranched starch dispersion was neutralized to $\text{pH } \sim 7$
155 with 0.1 M NaOH solution and then heated at $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in a thermomixer for 1 h to inactivate
156 the enzyme. Debranched samples were freeze-dried, dispersed in 1 mL DMSO/LiBr , and
157 injected into PSS GRAM 100 and 1000 columns connected in series, which had a
158 separation range of 100 to $\sim 10^6$ Da.

159 Data analysis and calculations to obtain SEC plots were performed as reported previously
160 by Wang, Hasjim, Wu, Henry, and Gilbert (2014) and Liu, Halley and Gilbert (2010).
161 The amylose content of the different starches was determined from the SEC molecular
162 size distribution of debranched starch as the ratio of the area under the curve (AUC) of
163 amylose branches to the AUC of overall amylopectin and amylose branches (International
164 Standardization Organization, 2011; Vilaplana, Hasjim, & Gilbert, 2012).

165 The degree of branching (DB) of whole starch molecules, defined as the percentage of α -
166 $(1 \rightarrow 6)$ glycosidic linkages (branching points) to the total of both α - $(1 \rightarrow 4)$ and α - $(1 \rightarrow 6)$
167 glycosidic linkages, was determined as the study performed by Wu et al. (2013).

168 **2.2.2 Thermal properties of retrograded gels**

169 Starch (8 mg) and distilled water ($13 \mu\text{l}$) were hermetically sealed in high volume
170 differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) pans. Sample pans were equilibrated for 1 h

171 before testing. Starch suspensions were analyzed in triplicate by DSC (TA Instruments
172 DSC 2920 Modulated DSC, New Castle, DE, USA) from 30 to 100 °C at a heating rate
173 of 10 °C/min (1st heat). An empty pan was used as a reference, and the system was
174 calibrated with indium. Pans were rapidly cooled to room temperature and then subjected
175 to the temperature cycle of 4 °C for 24 h followed by 25 °C for 24 h (2nd heat). This
176 temperature cycle was repeated for 7 days. Samples were then rescanned from 20 to 200
177 °C at 5 °C/min. An example of a thermogram showing an endotherm corresponding to
178 retrograded amylopectin is shown in supplementary material.

179 **2.2.3 Preparation of starch gels and retrograded starch**

180 Starch pastes (9.5% dry basis, d.b.) were formed by the addition of 2.66 g of each starch
181 to distilled water such that the final weight of the slurry was 28 g. Slurries were
182 gelatinized in a Rapid Visco Analyzer (RVA) Series 4.1 (Newport Scientific,
183 Warriewood, Australia) using a modified RVA heating profile (heating from 50 to 95 °C
184 at 13 °C/min and holding at 95 °C for 8 min 15 s at a mixing speed of 160 rpm).

185 RVA pastes were quickly poured onto a flat square of plexiglass, to which a polyvinyl
186 chloride ring (7.7 cm inner diameter and 0.25 cm high) was mounted. Pastes were spread
187 out evenly to fill the inner ring, and a second piece of plexiglass followed by a heavy flat
188 weight (2 kg) were placed on top of the ring (Matalanis et al., 2009). Samples were cooled
189 for 1 h at room temperature. Triplicate gel sheets were formed for each starch tested. After
190 cooling, disks (1.8 cm, diameter, 0.25 cm, high) were cut from starch gel sheets using a
191 plastic apple corer. At this point (day 1), gels obtained were either analyzed by dynamic
192 oscillatory testing or frozen in liquid nitrogen, freeze-dried, cryo-milled, and sieved
193 (120µm) to obtain powdered retrograded starch gel for *in vitro* digestion analysis. The
194 same procedure was followed to gels that were stored for 7 days (after the cooling down
195 period of 1 h) following temperature cycle as described in the DSC section (day 7).

196 **2.2.4 Dynamic oscillatory testing of starch gels**

197 A single disk of starch gel was placed inside a closed cell controlled stress rheometer
198 (Viscotech, Lund, Sweden) with 100 grit medium sand paper on the bottom and surface
199 of a 2.0 cm diameter parallel plate geometry to prevent sample slippage. A gap of 2.0 mm
200 was used. A frequency sweep from 0.1 to 60 Hz followed by a temperature sweep from
201 25 to 90 °C at 5 °C/min at a frequency of 1 Hz was performed. Both experiments were
202 performed at a maximum strain up to 10%, since initial strain sweeps showed that that
203 range was within the linear viscoelastic range for the tested samples. The storage modulus
204 (G'), representing the solid-like or elastic component of a material, was calculated from
205 the strain response of the material relative to the initial stress input. $\Delta G'$ was calculated
206 as the increase of G' over the storage time, i.e., G' at day 7 minus the corresponding G'
207 at day 1. G' drop was calculated after 7 days of storage as G' at 25 °C minus the
208 corresponding G' measured at 85 °C (supplementary material). Relative G' drop was
209 calculated as G' drop divided by G' at 25 °C and multiplied by 100. Coefficient of
210 variation among triplicate measurements was generally 15% or less.

211 **2.2.5 *In vitro* starch digestibility**

212 The rate and extent of starch amylolysis was determined *in vitro* as in Roman, Gomez,
213 Lee, Hamaker and Martinez (2017), involving sample digestion with porcine pancreatic
214 α -amylase and the quantification of digestion products through the determination of
215 reducing sugars. Enzymatic digestion was carried out using 0.16 unit of porcine
216 pancreatic α -amylase (type VI-B, A3176) per mg of starch. Native (ungelatinized) starch
217 samples were suspended in 10 mL of MOPS buffer (50 mM, pH 7) containing 0.02%
218 (w/v) sodium azide and calcium chloride (5 mM). The mixture was heated at 100 °C for
219 15 min to fully gelatinize the starch (as confirmed by DSC), cooled down for 10 min and
220 incubated at 37 °C with constant stirring at 350 rpm with a 3 mm×6 mm magnetic stirrer

221 bar. At defined time intervals, 50 μ L aliquots were immediately boiled at 100°C to stop
222 the enzymatic reaction. The supernatant was used to determine the reducing sugar content
223 using the dinitrosalicylic acid (DNS) method (Miller 1959). Only the first 60 min of
224 amylolysis was assayed, as this provided sufficient information for the application of the
225 different kinetic models. Powdered retrograded starch gels (50 mg) were assessed as
226 before but without the initial boiling step for 15 min, since samples were already fully
227 gelatinized. Tests were run in triplicate.

228 Starch amylolysis data of cooked fractions were fitted to a pseudo-first-order equation
229 [eq. (3), Goni, Garcia-Alonso, & Saura-Calixto, 1997]:

$$230 \quad C_t = C_\infty(1 - e^{-kt}) \text{ eq. 3}$$

231 where C_t is the concentration of product at a given time (t), C_∞ is the concentration of
232 product at the end of the reaction, and k is the digestibility rate constant.

233 **2.2.6 Cake-making, degree of starch gelatinization and starch digestibility**

234 Cakes consisted of 217.8 g starch, 99.5 g sucrose, 1.6 g sodium acid pyrophosphate, 1.1
235 g sodium bicarbonate, 0.9 g salt, 49.1 g water, 62.0 g whole eggs, 28.6 g glycerin, 45.4 g
236 canola oil, and 4.0 g lecithin. All ingredients except for oil and lecithin were mixed in a
237 Kitchen Aid Professional mixer KPM5 (St. Joseph, Michigan, USA) for 2 min at speed 2
238 and 1.5 min at speed 4. Oil and lecithin were then added and mixed for 1.5 min at speed
239 2. Cake batter (40 g) was placed into oil coated aluminum pans and the cakes were baked
240 in a convection oven for 14.5 min at 160 °C. After baking, cakes were removed from the
241 pans and left to cool for 20 min before being placed in coded plastic/aluminum bags that
242 were sealed to prevent drying.

243 To determine gelatinized starch content in the cakes (prepared as in section 2.2.6), the
244 cakes were crumbled by hand and placed with distilled water (50% solids content) into
245 TA Instruments Hastelloy-C screw-cap ampoules with Viton O-ring gaskets and screw-

246 capped. 500 mg of slurry were allowed to equilibrate for 15 min at room temperature and
247 placed into a TA Instruments Multi Cell DSC (MCDSC, TA Instruments, Crawley, UK),
248 calibrated for heat capacity using NIST 720 sapphire standards (temperature calibration
249 was verified previously with T_{onset} for the melting of ice within the range of ± 0.5 °C).
250 Nitrogen flow (meter reading set at 2 on the unit) was used to prevent moisture
251 condensation on the MCDSC cell. Samples were equilibrated for 10 min at 15 °C,
252 followed by heating to 135 °C (2 °C/min), cooling back to 15 °C and, after another 10 min
253 equilibration at 15 °C, re-heated to 135 °C (2 °C/min). The gelatinization enthalpy of cake
254 crumb was calculated as the enthalpy difference between the endotherms from first and
255 second heating steps on a total solid basis (ΔH_c). The same experimental protocol was
256 used to determine gelatinization enthalpy of the cake batter (ΔH_b). Samples were run in
257 triplicate.

258 The percent of gelatinized starch was then calculated using the following equation:

$$259 \quad \text{Gelatinized starch (\%)} = \left(1 - \frac{\Delta H_c}{\Delta H_b}\right) * 100 \text{ eq. 2}$$

260 The percentage of slowly digestible starch (SDS), resistant starch (RS) and total starch
261 (TS) was determined in native starches and cake crumb following the colorimetric
262 determination of the procedure proposed by Englyst, Kingman and Cummings (1992).

263 **2.2.6 Statistical analysis**

264 Differences between the parameters for the starches were studied by analysis of variance
265 (ANOVA). Fisher's least significant difference (LSD) was used to describe means with
266 95% confidence intervals. The statistical analysis was performed with Statgraphics
267 Centurion XVI software (Statpoint Technologies, Inc., The Plains, VA, USA).

268 **3 Results and discussion**

269 **3.1 Starch fine molecular structure.**

270 All SEC weight distributions were normalized to yield the same height of the highest peak
271 to expose detailed features and to facilitate qualitative comparison and interpretation (Fig.
272 1). Waxy starches did not show peaks corresponding to $R_h < 40$ nm [often associated to
273 amylose molecules (Cave, Seabrook, Gidley, & Gilbert, 2009)], suggesting negligible
274 amylose content (Fig. 1A). Meanwhile, acid-treated maize starches (low and high)
275 exhibited three peaks ($R_h \sim 10$, ~ 20 nm and ~ 47 nm) which may correspond to the
276 overlap of the peaks for hydrolyzed amylopectin and amylose and non-hydrolyzed
277 amylose molecules (Fig. 1A). SEC curves also revealed smaller molecules for high acid
278 maize than for lower acid maize (increase of the intensity of the peak at $R_h \sim 10$ and
279 reduction of the peak at ~ 47 nm), indicating that a more intense acid-conversion (likely
280 higher acid concentration) results in starch with significantly lower molecular size. The
281 branched SEC weight distribution of the rest of the starches exhibited two distinct peaks
282 for amylose and amylopectin molecules separated at $R_h \sim 40$ nm. R_h of amylose was in
283 the order of HAM70 < HAM50 < maize < rice < pea < wheat < potato < sago (Table 1). As for
284 amylopectin R_h , a clear peak of full amylopectin molecules with R_h values over 94.13 nm
285 was observed, except for acid-converted starches, whose amylopectin was hydrolyzed
286 (46.50 and 41.57 nm for low and high acid maize, respectively). The R_h of amylopectin
287 molecules of the rest of samples followed the order of
288 potato < sago < HAM70 < HAM50 < pea < rice < maize < waxy rice < wheat < waxy maize.
289
290

291

292 **Figure 1.** Size exclusion chromatograms of fully branched (A) and debranched starch
 293 samples (B), showing molecular size and unit chain length distribution of starch samples,
 294 respectively.

295 Typical chain length distributions of debranched starch molecules (Fig. 1B) show
 296 bimodal peaks representing short (peak $R_h \sim 1.5$ nm or DP ~ 16) and long (peak $R_h \sim 2.5$
 297 nm, DP ~ 50) amylopectin branches as well as amylose branches ($R_h \sim 5-80$ nm, DP
 298 $\sim 100-10,000$) (Wang et al., 2014). The main structural parameters are summarized in
 299 Table 1. No amylose peak was detected in waxy varieties. Meanwhile, acid maize starches

300 exhibited the shortest chains for amylose branches [$X_{AM}=352.4$ and 210 glucose units
301 (GU) for low and high acid maize starches, respectively], indicating that amylose chains
302 were hydrolyzed by the presence of acids during the production of this starch. In general,
303 X_{AM} followed a similar trend as R_h for amylose molecules. It is noteworthy that: 1) in
304 general, starches possessed a rather broad molecular weight distribution of the amylose
305 fraction and 2) the size of the polymers, more frequently reported as DP rather than
306 molecular weight values, differed both between and within botanical sources. The
307 amylose:amylopectin ratio was in the order of waxy maize < waxy
308 maize < potato < rice < sago < low acid maize < high acid
309 maize < wheat < pea < maize < HAM50 < HAM70. It is worth of mentions that the amylose
310 ratios of 37.7 and 48.2 for HAM 50 and HAM 70, respectively, were lower than expected
311 (50 and 70%). However, these modified starches contained intermediate materials (IM).
312 IM were reported to have molecular weights intermediate to amylopectin and amylose
313 and consisting of elongated branched polymers. IM chains apparently could be classified
314 as similar to those found in normal amylopectin, but the chain length of the chain
315 categories, especially the long chains, and the ratio of long chains/short chains are higher
316 (Perez & Bertoft, 2010) [see also Fig. 1B]. A complicating factor is that the methods for
317 the isolation of intermediate materials differs between laboratories and most certainly
318 affect the results reported. In general, samples exhibited significant differences in the
319 degree of branching (DB), being HAM 50 and HAM 70 characterized by having a
320 noticeable lower and rice and waxy rice a noticeable higher degree of branching compared
321 to the rest of the samples (Table 1). Significant differences were also observed for the
322 chain length distribution of amylopectin molecules among the different starches. HAM
323 50 and HAM 70 displayed longer X_{Ap1} (~19 GU), representing amylopectin short chains,
324 i.e., A and B1 chains, followed by potato (18.5 GU), sago (16.4 GU) and pea (15.5 GU),

325 than the rest of the starches ($X_{AP1} \leq 14.6$ GU). As for X_{AP2} , representing amylopectin long
326 chains, i.e., B2 and B3 chains, HAM 70 (47.5 GU), HAM 50 (44.6 GU) and potato (43.8
327 GU) starches displayed higher X_{AP2} than the rest of the starches, with values below 40.6
328 GU. These starches also exhibited a higher molar ratio of longer to short amylopectin
329 chains (h_{AP2}/h_{AP1}).

330 Table 1. Starch fine structure

331 Values with different letters in the same column are significantly different with $p < 0.05$.

	Average hydrodynamic radius (R_h) of whole (fully branched) starch		DP of peak maximum in SEC weight molecular size distribution of debranched starch					
	R_{hAM}	R_{hAP}	X_{Ap1}	X_{Ap2}	X_{Am}	DB (%)	$h_{AP2/hAP1}$	AM ratio (%)
Maize	13.32bc±0.12	123.23h±2.9	14.6bc±0.2	39.8abc±0.9	839.2ab±95.0	4.70b±0.44	0.53abc±0.06	33.9ef±7.5
Waxy maize	n.d.	130.75j±0.36	14.4bc±0.4	39.6abc±0.7	n.d.	5.80cd±0.65	0.54abc±0.04	0.7a±0.1
Low acid maize	n.a.	46.50b±0.71	14.2abc±0.1	38.4a±0.7	351.4a±92.6	4.68b±0.16	0.51ab±0.02	23.9c±1.7
High acid maize	n.a.	41.57a±0.81	14.2abc±0.1	39.3abc±0.2	210.0a±2.1	4.62b±0.23	0.53abc±0.00	24.5cd±2.7
HAM50	12.14ab±2.10	113.92ef±3.53	19.1e±0.1	44.6d±0.4	688.1ab±38.3	2.76a±0.27	0.93f±0.01	37.7f±0.6
HAM70	10.40a±0.40	111.32de±1.95	19.4e±2.2	47.5e±0.7	466.5a±268.4	2.14a±0.09	0.70d±0.02	48.2g±1.6
Rice	14.95c±0.17	118.78g±0.16	13.6bc±0.1	38.5a±0.1	837.8ab±198.7	6.14d±0.61	0.58bc±0.02	13.4b±2.9
Waxy rice	n.d.	124.30hi±0.68	13.7bc±0.3	39.1ab±0.2	n.d.	6.39d±0.07	0.58c±0.01	0.0a±0.0
Wheat	20.96d±0.41	127.88ij±0.55	13.0a±0.1	39.8abc±1.0	1713.0c±127.8	4.67b±0.17	0.59c±0.03	25.6cd±4.0
Potato	21.74d±1.05	94.13c±3.79	18.5e±0.0	43.8d±1.4	1560.9c±694.5	5.04bc±0.78	0.80e±0.03	10.8b±2.6
Sago	24.68e±0.80	108.82d±1.89	16.4d±0.1	40.6c±0.2	1316.8bc±337.4	4.85b±0.04	0.51a±0.03	21.4c±0.0
Pea	22.00d±0.00	116.64fg±1.26	15.5cd±0.3	40.1bc±0.2	1169.5bc±327.5	4.52b±0.35	0.52abc±0.05	30.4de±2.1

332 n.d., not detectable

333 n.a., peak not attributable exclusively to amylose molecules

334 X_{Ap1} , DP of peak maximum of short amylopectin chains, X_{Ap2} , DP of peak maximum of long amylopectin chains, X_{AM} , DP of peak maximum of

335 amylose chains, DB, degree of branching, $h_{AP2/hAP1}$, height of A_{p2} in SEC weight molecular size distribution of debranched starch as ratio to A_{p1}

336 peak height.

337 **3.2 Thermal properties of retrograded gels**

338 DSC data for cooked and retrograded starches are summarized in Table 2. DSC
339 measurements were carried out at ~60% starch concentration, since the maximum extent
340 of starch recrystallization has been shown to occur between 50 and 60% starch
341 concentration (Gudmundsson & Eliasson, 1991; Longton & Legrys, 1981). The enthalpy
342 of amylopectin retrogradation, which reflects the thermal energy associated with
343 crystallite melting and dissociation/unraveling of double helices [resulting from
344 disruption of inter- and intra-helical hydrogen bonds (Cooke & Gidley, 1992)], was
345 similar for most samples. Only HAM 50, HAM 70 and potato exhibited higher
346 temperatures (T_0 , T_p and T_c) for the melting of double helices. The highest X_{AP1} , X_{AP2}
347 and ($h_{AP2/hAP1}$) of these samples indicates that longer chains result in longer and more
348 stable double helices. Enthalpic transitions for retrograded starch gels were significantly
349 different among samples, and displayed the order of
350 HAM70<wheat<HAM50<rice<waxy rice<maize<low acid maize<pea<high acid
351 maize<sago<potato<waxy maize. It is of worth mentioning that HAM starches do not
352 fully gelatinize during cooking with the conventional RVA used in this study, so the
353 enthalpy values attributed to AP retrogradation could likely be underestimated. In this
354 case, the amount of amylopectin (negatively correlated with the amylose:amylopectin
355 ratio) was positively associated with the enthalpic signal intensity, which could mask the
356 effect of the chain length distribution.

357 Table 2. Thermal properties of retrograded starch gels

		Maize	Waxy maize	Low acid maize	High acid maize	HAM50	HAM70	Rice	Waxy rice	Wheat	Potato	Sago	Pea
RAP	T ₀ (°C)	47.8a±0.2	45.3a±0.1	46.9a±0.8	46.4a±0.2	49.5ab±0.9	53.4b±6.1	47.6a±0.3	45.7a±0.6	47.3a±0.6	49.4ab±0.1	46.9a±0.0	49.1a±2.2
	T _p (°C)	55.9de±0.0	54.4abc±0.1	55.2bcd±0.3	55.8cde±0.1	59.6fg±0.4	58.9f±1.6	55.0abcd±0.3	53.9a±0.3	54.3ab±0.2	60.6g±0.1	56.3de±0.1	56.9e±1.2
	T _c (°C)	66.7bc±2.1	67.1bc±0.1	69.2cd±1.1	71.0d±0.1	76.0g±2.4	76.9g±1.3	65.1ab±0.4	63.7a±0.2	65.4ab±1.0	80.5h±0.1	73.0f±0.9	75.8g±1.2
	ΔH (J/g)	3.8e±0.2	5.9g±0.1	4.5f±0.1	5.0f±0.0	2.2bc±0.5	1.0a±0.2	2.5c±0.1	3.1d±0.3	1.9b±0.0	5.8g±0.3	5.6g±0.2	4.9f±0.4
ACI	T ₀ (°C)	93.5b±1.6	n.d.	94.3bc±1.0	96.2cd±0.5	98.0de±1.0	97.6de±0.2	80.9a±0.0	n.d.	99.2e±0.0	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
	T _p (°C)	102.3b±0.1	n.d.	102.1b±0.0	102.6b±0.3	103.2b±0.5	103.0b±0.1	95.4a±6.4	n.d.	104.3b±0.1	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
	T _c (°C)	109.4ab±0.8	n.d.	109.0ab±0.8	107.9a±0.5	110.5b±2.0	108.9ab±0.2	109.0ab±0.3	n.d.	110.7b±0.6	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
	ΔH (J/g)	1.1a±0.0	n.d.	1.0a±0.2	0.6a±0.1	1.0a±0.5	0.6a±0.0	1.7b±0.4	n.d.	0.8a±0.1	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
ACII	T ₀ (°C)	n.d.	n.d.	115.2b±1.1	115.3b±0.8	116.2b±0.0	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
	T _p (°C)	n.d.	n.d.	121.4a±3.6	119.2a±0.1	121.0a±0.0	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
	T _c (°C)	n.d.	n.d.	127.5a±3.5	125.6a±0.7	127.7a±1.7	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
	ΔH (J/g)	n.d.	n.d.	0.4a±0.1	0.5a±0.2	0.2a±0.1	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.

358 Values with different letters in the same row are significantly different with $p < 0.05$.

359 n.d., not detectable

360 T₀, onset temperature, T_p, peak temperature, T_c, conclusion temperature, ΔH, enthalpy; RAP, retrograded amylopectin, ACI, type I amylose-lipid

361 complexes; type II ACI amylose-lipid complexes.

362 DSC of some samples showed an additional thermal dissociation occurring in a
363 temperature region (100-120 °C) attributed to the melting of the amylose–lipid
364 complexes. These are different from those of the endothermic transitions of native A- or
365 B-crystallites of amylopectin and retrograded amylopectin (40-55° C) or amylose (140-
366 160° C). In the native starch granule, the starch–lipid complex is in an amorphous state
367 and amylose-lipid helices are not organized into a crystalline packing, which are the so-
368 called type I complexes with low-temperature (<105 °C) melting endotherms (Buleon,
369 Colonna, Planchot, & Ball, 1998). In the present study, only non-waxy maize, wheat and
370 rice starches displayed an endotherm corresponding to amylose-lipid complexes, which
371 was especially high in rice starch. Type I complexes can be, in some cases, annealed into
372 a more ordered semi-crystalline form that melts at higher temperatures (~120 °C), the so-
373 called type II amylose-lipid complexes (Biliaderis & Galloway, 1989). Except in high-
374 amylose maize starch (Zobel, 1992), type II complexes are rarely seen in native samples.
375 In the present study, together with HAM 50, acid-converted maize starches displayed an
376 endotherm corresponding to the aforementioned type II complexes (Table 2). This
377 occurrence indicates that acid-conversion, generally performed below gelatinization
378 temperatures, anneal type I complexes into a more ordered semi-crystalline form.

379 **3.3. Dynamic rheology test for starch intermolecular associations.**

380 A more direct indication of retrogradation as it influences texture is found in data from
381 dynamic oscillatory test in pastes/gels (Table 3). Unlike the enthalpic transitions for the
382 melting of both intra- and inter-molecular amylopectin double helices, the evolution of
383 the storage modulus (G') of starch pastes/gels is influenced by amylopectin-amylopectin,
384 amylose-amylose, and amylopectin-amylose intermolecular interactions that form gel
385 structure. In a freshly prepared aqueous solution, the amylose chain adopts a random coil
386 structure (Hayashi, Kinoshita, & Miyake, 1981), which is, however, not stable. In this

387 scenario, amylose molecules have been reported to gradually associate with each other,
388 with a rate that depends on their molecular size (Goodman & Garcia, 1991; Leloup,
389 Colonna, & Buleon, 1991; Milles, Morris, & Ring, 1984, 1985ab; Ring, Miles, Morris,
390 Turner, & Colonna, 1987) and concentration. Furthermore, interactions with long
391 amylopectin chains may also occur, although its contribution in gel structure has been
392 less studied. At early stages of interaction (day 1), intermolecular junctions were already
393 formed and, albeit short, they contributed to a comparatively high G' in gels made with
394 HAM 50, HAM 70 and pea starches, followed by wheat and maize starches, which
395 possessed the highest amylose:amylopectin ratio (Table 1). It is also noteworthy that
396 amylose retrogrades faster than amylopectin (Miles et al., 1985ab; Jacobson, Obanni, &
397 BeMiller, 1997) and may greatly contribute to the formation of gel structure (junction
398 zones) at the early stages of storage.

399 Table 3. Rheology and digestibility of retrograded starch gels

	Maize	Waxy maize	Low acid maize	High acid maize	HAM50	HAM70	Rice	Waxy rice	Wheat	Potato	Sago	Pea
G' day 1 (Pa)	3605.4c±359.4	21.3a±1.8	3104.2bc±147.4	3047.9bc±209.2	21678.8e±2394.4	9329.1d±3114.4	271.4a±12.2	47.8a±1.1	3543.2c±80.3	1258.7abc±83.0	974.5ab±6.3	8762.6d±159.3
G' day 7 (Pa)	24090.8cd±11.7	71.9a±2.7	24175.6cd±1728.6	28729.0de±4735.5	109249.0h±2965.6	38035.8f±1003.2	361.4a±31.7	27.9a±0.8	7959.2b±54.5	21795.3c±739.4	32382.5e±1617.6	51597.5g±5830
ΔG' (Pa)	20485.4b±347.6	50.6a±0.8	21071.4b±1876.0	25681.1bc±4944.7	87570.2e±5360.0	28706.6c±417.5	90.0a±9.5	-19.9a±1.9	4416.0a±13.4	20536.6b±822.4	31408.0c±1624.0	42834.9d±5671.7
G' drop (Pa)	20520.1c±898.0	62.3a±0.4	21764.2c±1918.5	26533.9d±4617.5	80883.1g±2931.3	20985.9c±557.8	6.2a±1.9	6.9a±2.4	4239.1b±48.0	19896.0c±298.4	31351.9e±1666.4	46184.1f±2307.9
Relative G' drop (%)	85.6ef±3.5	86.8efg±2.5	89.7efg±2.1	92.6gh±0.1	72.6d±1.3	54.1c±2.6	1.7a±0.4	25.0b±8.3	53.3c±0.9	91.6fgh±1.5	97.3h±0.0	84.5e±0.4
k reduction (%)	26.9b±1.9	16.0a±0.4	51.8ef±2.1	51.6ef±3.1	33.3bc±4.4	44.1de±2.2	41.0cd±2.0	38.5cd±4.2	10.2a±2.5	57.3fg±4.3	64.7g±4.3	55.1f±8.1
C_∞ reduction (%)	18.4de±2.4	10.9bc±2.3	17.4cd±1.8	15.5cd±4.4	41.7g±5.7	34.0f±2.2	8.1ab±0.2	19.8de±6.9	2.8a±3.5	33.4f±0.6	6.3ab±0.5	24.8e±1.6

400 Values with different letters in the same row are significantly different with $p < 0.05$.

401 G'1, storage modulus of gels at day 1, G'7, storage modulus of gels at day 7, ΔG', G'7-G'1, Δk, decrease of digestion rate of gels from day 1 to

402 day 7; ΔC_∞, decrease of equilibrium concentration of gels from day 1 to day 7.

403 Later, as retrogradation proceeds for 24 h, these junctions extend significantly in length,
404 and simultaneously additional intermolecular bridges are established, which markedly
405 increases G' . HAM 50 and pea starches exhibited the highest G' increase from day 1 to
406 day 7 ($\Delta G'$), followed by sago and HAM 70. There was not a single structural factor that
407 could explain the reasons for these gels to have the greatest $\Delta G'$. HAM and pea starches
408 possessed the highest amylose ratio together with maize, the latter not showing high $\Delta G'$.
409 Interestingly, gels made with sago starch exhibited a 31408 Pa $\Delta G'$, suggesting that,
410 alongside a high amylose ratio, an intermediate amylose length (1100-1400 GU) could
411 result in greater amylose intermolecular junctions that form gel structure. This is in
412 agreement with the results found by Clark, Gidley, Richardson and Ross-Murphy (1989),
413 who studied G' development over time of monodispersed amylose varying in chain length
414 and found that amyloses with an intermediate length of DP 1100 exhibited the highest G'
415 development. These authors stated that in very long amylose chains (DP > 1100)
416 relatively few cross-links are required before aggregate diffusion becomes significantly
417 retarded, thereby slowing down subsequent cross-link and modulus increase.

418 When freshly prepared (cooled 1 h) starch gels were subjected to a temperature sweep
419 from 25 to 90 °C, no thermal transition was observed in the temperature range of 40–60
420 °C, the temperature range for melting retrograded amylopectin (data not shown).
421 Furthermore, no significant differences were found between G' of samples at 90 °C for
422 freshly prepared gels and G' at 90 °C for gels aged 7 days (data not shown). These results
423 are in agreement with those reported by Matalanis et al. (2009) studying maize, rice and
424 sorghum starches. These two findings indicate that the initial starch gel texture is solely
425 the result of amylose and not amylopectin retrogradation. A temperature sweep of
426 retrograded samples stored for 7 days further revealed a decrease of G' (supplementary
427 material, Table 3), which is the result of loss, or melting, of intermolecular associations

428 (double helices) among amylopectin molecules (or amylopectin and amylose). It is
429 noteworthy that, although the formation of intramolecular helices along external starch
430 chains (A and B1 chains) increase enthalpic transitions of retrograded starches (Klucinec
431 & Thompson, 2002), no correlation was observed between enthalpy and G' loss. Klucinec
432 and Thompson (2002) and Matalanis et al. (2009) noted that the formation of
433 intramolecular helices has little impact on G' values for aged starch gels, since this type
434 of re-association does not contribute to the network structure of a starch gel. HAM 50,
435 pea, sago and high acid-converted maize exhibited the greatest G' loss (Table 3). In order
436 to avoid a masking effect of the initial G' value (initial gel strength of gels before heating),
437 results were normalized to the G' at 25 °C (G' drop divided by G' at 25 °C and multiplied
438 by 100), and the value of relative G' drop was obtained. This better depicts the loss of gel
439 structure during heating that is due to the disassembling of intermolecular double helices of
440 amylopectin molecules, regardless of the initial gel structure that may have been
441 influenced by the amylose network. Sago, potato and high acid-converted maize
442 displayed the highest relative G' drop, suggesting that the amylopectin of these starches
443 is heavily involved in intermolecular interactions that form gel structure. Interestingly,
444 sago and potato were the only starches with an amylose ratio close to 20% or lower that
445 possessed X_{AP1} and X_{AP2} higher than 16 and 40 GU, respectively. It is therefore believed
446 that amylopectin with longer A and B1 chains as well as B2 and B3 chains are prone to
447 more intermolecular associations. Investigations have shown that starches with longer
448 amylopectin chains retrograde more quickly than those with short amylopectin chains
449 (Fredriksson, Silverio, Andersson, Eliasson, & Aman, 1998; Kalichevsky, Orford, &
450 Ring, 1990; Silverio, Fredriksson, Andersson, Eliasson, & Aman, 2000). In the case of
451 acid-converted maize, it seems that small molecular size of amylose and amylopectin

452 molecules may have a crucial promoting role in developing gel structure, likely because
453 of their smaller size and therefore higher mobility and better alignment properties.

454 **3.4. Starch digestibility of starch samples**

455 In many intermediate/high moisture food products, conventional hydrothermal
456 processing, such as baking, promotes partial or complete starch gelatinization. Varriano-
457 Marston et al. (1980) reported degrees of starch gelatinization (DG) of 75 % in yellow
458 cake crumb (intermediate moisture product), whereas sugar cookie (low moisture
459 product) displayed only 11% DG. Recently, Martinez et al. (2018) reported complete
460 starch gelatinization (100% DG) in the crumb of white bread, even made at low hydration
461 levels (45%). Therefore, an array of baked food products possess starch with an
462 amorphous structure highly susceptible to enzyme hydrolysis (Baldwin et al., 2015;
463 Roman et al., 2017). Considering the negative implications of frequent consumption of
464 rapid digestible starch on human health, the formation of starch that is more slowly
465 digested from fully gelatinized material would be expected to reduce postprandial
466 glycaemia. Starch digestibility was assessed in fully gelatinized material without storage
467 and after a 7 day storage period with the aim of obtaining a mechanistic understanding of
468 the contribution of starch structure-interactions relationships in slowing down starch
469 digestibility (Table 3). As discussed before, it is important to highlight that HAM starches
470 did not fully gelatinize during cooking with the conventional RVA used in this study, so
471 the slow digestion of HAM starches could also result from un-gelatinized material. All
472 starch samples, regardless of storage time, were digested by pancreatic α -amylase
473 following an exponential curve. Moreover, all samples showed a reduction in the
474 digestion rate during storage ranging from 10.2 to 64.7 %, depending on the starch source
475 (supplementary material). Interestingly, this reduction was particularly evident in sago
476 (64.7 %), potato (57.3 %), pea (55.1 %), low acid-converted maize (51.8 %) and high acid

477 converted maize (51.6 %). A reduction of starch susceptibility to enzyme hydrolysis
478 through retrogradation has already been shown (Farhat et al., 2001; Okuda, Aramaki,
479 Koseki, Inouchi, & Hashizume, 2006). Sago, potato and pea starches, differing in
480 amylose:amylopectin ratio (10.8-30.4%) and amylose length (1169-1560 GU), contained
481 amylopectin with significantly longer A and B1 chains (X_{API}) than the rest of the starches.
482 Although HAM starches contained longer amylopectin A and B1 chains, starch granules
483 were not fully gelatinized during RVA cooking (data not shown), which enables less
484 dispersed amylopectin molecules available to re-associate during retrogradation.
485 Moreover, the high amylose:amylopectin ratio (low amylopectin content) may have
486 caused the formation of resistant structures to digestion (non-digestible resistant starch),
487 rather than slowly digestible starch. In this way, it seems that the amylopectin of normal
488 starches (those from plants without modified starch biosynthesis) with an external A and
489 B1 chain population of a DP of peak maximum at ≥ 15.5 GU interact through the
490 formation of double helices (as seen by high enthalpic values in Table 2) that also are
491 prone to forming intermolecular associations, perhaps involving internal long chains (as
492 seen in Table 2 by a high relative G' drop). Of note, the internal chain length distribution
493 of amylopectin, and particularly inter-block chain length, is likely important to these
494 associations (Vamadevan & Bertoft, 2018). Although the amylopectin of acid-converted
495 maize starches exhibited high enthalpic values (presence of amylopectin double helices)
496 and high relative G' drop (intermolecular double helical associations), they did not fit to
497 this structure-function relationship. Perhaps the high mobility and better aligning
498 properties of small hydrolyzed molecules (either amylopectin or amylose) increases
499 interactions that decrease starch bioaccessibility.

500 The extension of starch hydrolysis as an indicator of the total digestible starch
501 [represented by the equilibrium concentration (C_{∞}) at the end of the digestogram

(supplementary material)] also decreased during storage, with reduction percentages ranging from 2.8 to 41.7 %. In particular, HAM50, HAM 70 and potato starches exhibited the highest reduction in C_{∞} compared to the rest of the starches. It is well known that amylose chains tend to form thermally and enzymatically stable double helical structures (Haralampu, 2000; Patel et al., 2017), which would explain this reduction for HAM starches, with amylose ratio ≥ 37.7 %. In the case of potato, it seems that high X_{AP1} , X_{AP2} , $h_{AP2/AP1}$ and X_{AM} jointly foster in intra- or intermolecular associations that result in enzymatically resistant starch structures that slow digestion. It is noteworthy that the decrease of starch digestion rate (k) during storage could be also attributed to the potential contribution of retrograded amylose in impairing the catalytic efficiency of α -amylase. In 2017, Patel et al. found that a purified sample of retrograded high amylose starch inhibited amylase directly and that amylase binds to retrograded amylose. They reported a linear inhibition of amylase, which implies interaction at a single site on the enzyme. However, the enzyme kinetics could not provide direct information about the site on α -amylase to which HAM binds.

Table 4. Starch digestion fractions of maize and sago starches and cakes (stored for 1 and 24 h after baking), accompanied by calculated degree of starch gelatinization in cake crumb and estimated values of SDS.

	Native starches		Cakes			
	Maize	Sago	1 h after baking		24 h after baking	
			Maize	Sago	Maize	Sago
SDS (%)	62.5±0.5	21.2±1.0	6.1a±1.4	7.4a±0.1	5.5a±0.4	11.2b±2.4
RS (%)	12.7±2.5	75.1±1.0	-	-	0.8a±	4.5b±
TS (%)	99.8±3.1	100.7±1.0	-	-	45.6a±	46.3a±
GS (%)	-	-	-	-	33a±11	20a±7
ESDS _{gel} (%)	-	-	-	-	0	54

520

521 Values with different letters in the same row are significantly different with $p < 0.05$.

522 SDS, slowly digestible starch; RS, resistant starch; TS, total starch; GS, gelatinized
523 starch; ESDS, estimated SDS in cake crumb, $ESDS_{gel}$, estimated SDS from gelatinized
524 starch (formed throughout retrogradation).

525 In this study, a potential application of this starch structure-digestibility relationships was
526 also demonstrated. Maize and sago starch-based cakes were made and served as a model
527 to evidence the formation of SDS during storage from fully gelatinized material in a real
528 food. These starches were chosen because no significant differences were found in their
529 degree of starch gelatinization in cake crumb (Table 4), which is a factor that could
530 influence differences in SDS after baking. A mass balance for SDS was performed to
531 obtain the estimated/theoretical SDS from ungelatinized/native starch (ESDS) in the cake
532 crumb (eq. 4):

$$533 \quad ESDS = TS \cdot \left(\frac{UG}{100}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{SDS_0}{100}\right) \quad \text{eq. 4}$$

534 where TS is total starch in the cake crumb, UG is the amount of ungelatinized starch (%)
535 and SDS_0 is the SDS content (%) in the native starch. ESDS was then used in eq. 5 to
536 obtain the estimated/theoretical SDS that comes from fully gelatinized starch ($ESDS_{gel}$):

$$537 \quad ESDS_{gel} = 100 - \left[\left(\frac{ESDS}{SDS_c} \right) \cdot 100 \right] \quad \text{eq. 5}$$

538 where ESDS is the estimated/theoretical SDS from ungelatinized/native starch (ESDS) in
539 the cake crumb (%) and SDS_c is the SDS analyzed in the crumb of cakes.

540 Results from the theoretical calculations suggested that that up 56% of SDS in sago cake
541 crumb stored for 1 week comes from gelatinized starch, whereas no SDS formation from
542 gelatinized material was suggested for maize cake. Experimental results confirmed this
543 mathematical estimation, where a significant increase in SDS was only observed in sago
544 cake during the first 24 h of storage after baking (Table 4). Therefore, for the first time,

545 scientific evidence of the formation of SDS from fully gelatinized starch based on starch
546 structure-interactions relationships is reported.

547

548 **4 Conclusions**

549 Many intermediate/high moisture food products are hydrothermally processed before
550 consumption. As a result, the native starch macromolecular structure, acting as a natural
551 physical barrier to enzyme digestion, is lost and leads to foods with high glycemic index.

552 This study provides unique mechanistic understanding on structure-digestion
553 relationships of fully gelatinized starch and the formation of slowly digestible

554 macromolecular structures after gelatinization. Results suggested that the amylopectin of
555 normal starches (those from plants without modified starch biosynthesis) with an external

556 A and B1 chain population with DP of peak maximum at ≥ 15.5 GU interact through the
557 formation of double helices that also are prone to forming intermolecular associations,

558 perhaps involving internal long chains. This finding would allow food manufacturers to
559 optimize a starch source (which may potentially be clean label) in order to increase the
560 amount of structurally-driven slowly digestible starch through retrogradation.

561 Furthermore, acid-converted maize starch also exhibited an interesting potential to form
562 intermolecular associations that are slowly digestible, which was attributed to the better
563 alignment and mobility properties of starch acid-hydrolyzed molecules with smaller size.

564 For the first time, starches have been identified with specific structural features that result
565 in slowly digestible macromolecular structures after gelatinization through
566 retrogradation.

567

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